

Stability of Chelate Compounds of Substituted Salicylaldehydes with Bivalent Metal Ions

P. V. Kamat*, N. B. Laxmeshwar, M. G. Datar

Proton-ligand stability constants of substituted salicylaldehydes are found to vary in the following order, viz., 5-NO₂ < 3-NO₂ < 5-SO₃H < 4-NO₂ Salicylaldehyde at 30°, and at ionic strength $\mu 0.1M$ NaClO₄ in a mixed solvent 75% dioxane—25% water (V/V). The metal ligand stability order is Cu > Zn > Mn > Mg have been observed for these ligands without any exception.

Stability constants of the chelate formation by reagents containing OH-COCH₃, OH-CHO, etc. have been reported in the literature¹⁻¹⁰.

In present study an attempt is made to determine the structural relationship with respect to substituents in benzene nucleus on the strength of metal-reagent bond formation. For this purpose salicylaldehyde, 3-nitro, 4-nitro, 5-nitro, and 5-sulphosalicylaldehydes, are made to react with bivalent metal ions like copper, zinc, magnesium and manganese, in the form of metal perchlorates.

EXPERIMENTAL

Chemicals used were all of Analar quality (May and Baker) and were further purified by standard methods. For the measurements of variation in pH during the course of titrations, 'ELICO' pH meter, model LI-10, with Beckmann glass-calomel electrode assembly to read from pH 0-14, was used. The reagents were prepared in dioxane while those of metal perchlorates in 0.16 M perchloric acid. Three sets of usual experiments were performed in each case of complex formation.

* Present Address : Ciba Research Centre, Goregaon (East,) Bombay-63, India.

1. N. V. Sidgwick and R. K. Callow, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **125**, 527.
2. P. Pfeiffer, E. Breith, E. Llibbe and T. Trumaki, *Ann*, 1933, **503**, 84; *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1931, **129**, 163; *ibid.*, 1938, **151**, 313, *ibid.*, 1939, **153**, 265, 300. *ibid.*, 1940, **155**, 77, *ibid.*, 1941, **157**, 97. *ibid.*, 1942, **162**, 279.
3. M. Calvin and K. W. Wilson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 2003.
4. P. Pfeiffer, *Angew. Chem.*, 1940, **53**, 93.
5. N. V. Sidgwick, *Ann. Reports on Progress of Chem. Soc.*, London, 1934, **31**, 41.
6. W. Baker, E. H. T. Jukes and C. T. Subramanian. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1680.
7. G. E. Hilbert, O. R. Watt, S. B. Hendricks and U. Liddel, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **58**, 548.
8. P. V. Kamat, M. R. Bapat and M. G. Datar, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 731.
9. M. Calvin and N. C. Melchoir, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 3270.
10. L. C. Van Ultert and W. C. Fernelius, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 375.
11. A. I. Vogel. A text book of Practical Org. Chem., Longmans, Green and Co., 1956.
12. H. M. Irving and H. S. Rosotti, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From the results reported in Table I, the order in proton-ligand stability constants of various salicylaldehydes may be written as $5\text{-NO}_2 < 3\text{-NO}_2 < 5\text{-SO}_3\text{H} < 4\text{-NO}_2 < \text{salicylaldehyde}$. On substitution in benzene ring, the electron withdrawing groups like -NO_2 , the intramolecular hydrogen bond formation may be affected and this effect may markedly be observed by the change in the dissociation constant of the reagent. In the present case the phenomenon may be as follows :

TABLE I

Data on Proton-ligand stability constants

Reagent	Method	T°C	Solvent	pK
Salicylaldehyde	gl	30	75% dioxane	12.22
3-nitro-	gl	30	75% dioxane	6.1
4-nitro-	gl	30	75% dioxane	7.5
5-nitro-	gl	30	75% dioxane	6.0
5-sulpho-	gl	30	75% dioxane	7.4

(gl.; potentiometric method by glass-calomel electrode).

The strength of the hydrogen bond depends upon such and allied factors and plays an important part in release of proton. This is also evident from the results. The pK values of 3- NO_2 and 5- NO_2 -salicylaldehyde are approximately equal i.e., 6.1 and 6.0, while that of 4- NO_2 -salicylaldehyde is 7.5. Thus the difference in pK by about 1.4-1.5 log units supports the assumption of substituted -NO_2 having minimum effect in meta position.

One finds that the pK value for $\text{-SO}_3\text{H}$ substitution is higher by 1.4 log units indicating more proton release than for NO_2 substitution. Literature values for these compounds¹³⁻¹⁵ are quite close to those obtained here.

13. L. E. Maley and D. P. Mellor, *Austral. J. Sci. Res.*, 1949, **2A**, 92.

14. S. E. Turner and R. C. Anderson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 912.

15. D. P. Mellor and L. E. Maley, *Nature*, 1947, **159**, 370, *ibid.*, 1948, **161**, 436.

TABLE II

Data on metal-ligand stability constants

Temp. 30°	$\mu \sim 0.1 M \text{ NaClO}_4$	Metal-ligand = 1:4		
Reagent	Metal ion	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta_2$
Salicylaldehyde ($pK = 12.22$)	Mg	6.30	4.35	10.65
	Mn	6.89	5.70	12.59
	Cu	10.40	8.40	18.80
	Zn	7.55	5.95	13.50
3-nitro- Salicylaldehyde ($pK = 6.1$)	Mg	4.11	—	5.88
	Mn	4.51	—	6.23
	Cu	4.82	3.42	8.24
	Zn	4.63	—	8.11
4-nitro- Salicylaldehyde ($pK = 7.5$)	Mg	4.22	—	6.58
	Mn	4.70	—	7.20
	Cu	5.63	4.25	9.88
	Z	5.42	—	8.97
5-nitro- Salicylaldehyde ($pK = 6.00$)	Mg	3.37	—	5.30
	Mn	3.80	—	6.12
	Cu	4.80	3.87	8.47
	Zn	4.34	—	7.90
5-sulpho- Salicylaldehyde ($pK = 7.4$)	Mg	2.70	—	4.75
	Mn	2.85	—	5.40
	Cu	5.50	4.05	9.55
	Zn	3.10	—	5.50

Burger and coworkers¹⁶ have reported some values of dissociation constants of substituted salicylaldoximes by infrared and ultra-violet methods. The decrease in the order of hydrogen bonds of the derivatives of salicylaldoxime was $5\text{-CH}_3 > \text{H} > 3\text{-NO}_2$. Values obtained in the present investigation are also in agreement with the reported ones viz., $\text{H} > 5\text{-NO}_2$. Metal-ligand stability constants obtained in the present work are in agreement with the natural series proposed by earlier investigators¹⁷⁻¹⁹.

Physical Chemistry Department,
Institute of Science,
Bombay-32.

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16. Kalman Burger and coworkers, *Magy. Kem. Folyoirat* 1965, **71**, (7) 292; C.A. 63 : 14347.
17. H. Irving and R. J. P. Williams, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3192.
18. D. D. Perrin, *Nature*, 1958, **182**, 741.
19. A. Albert, *Nature*, 1959, **184**, 440.